

Executive Summary

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1. Introduction

Recent years witness an upsurge in the quantities of digital research data, offering new insights and opportunities for improved understanding. Text and data mining is emerging as a powerful tool for harnessing the power of structured and unstructured content and data, by analysing them at multiple levels and in several dimensions to discover hidden and new knowledge. However, text mining solutions are not easy to discover and use, nor are they easily combinable by end users. OpenMinTeD aspires to enable the creation of an infrastructure that fosters and facilitates the use of text mining technologies in the scientific publications world, builds on existing text mining tools and platforms, and renders them discoverable and interoperable through appropriate registries and a standards-based interoperability layer, respectively. It supports training of text mining users and developers alike and demonstrates the merits of the approach through several use cases identified by scholars and experts from different scientific areas, ranging from generic scholarly communication to literature related to life sciences, food and agriculture, and social sciences and humanities.

Figure 1: OpenMinTeD bringing together and bridging gaps between technologies and communities

Through its infrastructural activities, OpenMinTeD’s vision is to make operational a virtuous cycle in which:

- a. primary content is accessed through standardised interfaces and access rules
- b. by well-documented and easily discoverable text mining services that process, analyse, and annotate text
- c. to identify patterns and extract new meaningful actionable knowledge, which will be used
- d. for structuring, indexing, and searching content and, in tandem,

- e. acting as new knowledge useful to draw new relations between content items and firing a new mining cycle.

To achieve its goals, OpenMinTeD brings together different stakeholders, content providers and scientific communities, text mining and infrastructure builders, legal experts, data and computing centres, industrial players, and SMEs.

OpenMinTeD achievements in a nutshell:

From its onset, OpenMinTeD was designed to bring and bridge gaps between TDM technologies, services, systems, communities, all under the consideration of a strong legal framework. This was achieved and will be further developed as OpenMinTeD is a dynamic system with a broad user base. OpenMinTeD currently offers access to 14 Million publications (via OpenAIRE and CORE) via integrated TDM frameworks (UIMA, GATE); registered more than 28 TDM applications targeting 5 research areas, and more than 190 TDM components ready to be integrated in more complex workflows; produced more than 45 training and tutorial material; analysed more than 13 licenses on content, 13 licenses on software and 8 on services, resulting to a legal compatibility matrix.

General overview

During the project's three-year duration all consortium members worked towards a common goal: to create a TDM e-infrastructure "OpenMinTeD", a preamble to the European Open Science Cloud, that enables the registration and deployment of existing TDM tools and applications, the connection to Open Access scientific content, allowing various stakeholders (Researchers, Open Access publishers, librarians, repository managers and Small Medium Enterprises) to seamlessly discover, share, analyse and re-use knowledge. All well-presented and operating on a cloud infrastructure (~okeanos by GRNET). This was achieved through the **OpenMinTeD Interoperability Guidelines**¹, which address interoperability aspects for content and services. Furthermore, OpenMinTeD has elaborated **a license compatibility matrix** to investigate the compatibility among licenses on content, software and services, a service that may be used in other data infrastructures as well.

¹ guidelines.openminded.eu

Two scientific advisory boards were held to provide feedback and guidance on critical challenges. The information from advisors triggered some of the functionalities of OpenMinTeD and enhanced its capabilities.

2. The OpenMinTeD e-Infrastructure

2.1 Platform

OpenMinTeD platform as an e-Infrastructure, is accessible to all in the portal: <https://services.openminted.eu/>. Additional material with more analysis on the services and blogs, news, are in a dedicated website: <http://openminted.eu/>.

2.2 Policies

OpenMinTeD defined and organised a **set of policies and rules of engagement**² that are publicly available to all in the form of FAQs. The information reflects what the users can perform, based on latest legal and technical requirements and vision and mission of OpenMinTeD principles.

2.3 Dissemination and Communication

Communication and dissemination

A plan on diverse set of activities to raise awareness about the project (via social media, blogs, posts, announcements), its outcomes and opportunities, was designed. Goal was to facilitate the participation in activities of collaboration with international and other EU initiatives and RIs related to open science, text mining, natural language processing, language technologies, cloud and data infrastructures. Creating synergies with other initiatives to maximise projects impact in multiple domains of interest and building the instruments (i.e. tender calls) for the uptake of the infrastructure interoperability framework and platform was a priority. Moreover, a series of workshops, events, and presentations in conferences and a launch event of the OpenMinTeD platform were organised.

2.4 Collaborations

OpenMinTeD is in close collaboration with major EU projects and initiatives: OpenAIRE³ and CORE⁴ for access to content, FutureTDM⁵

Figure 2: OpenMinTeD Social media

² <http://openminted.eu/policies-and-rules-of-engagement/>

³ <https://www.openaire.eu/>

⁴ <https://core.ac.uk/>

⁵ <https://www.futuretdm.eu/>

for legal advising, METASHARE⁶ and CLARIN⁷ for language resources, ELIXIR⁸ for commonalities on TDM services, e-Infracentral⁹ for service catalogue, FOSTER¹⁰ for training platform, GEANT¹¹ and EOSC-hub¹² for AAI.

2.5 Legal

OpenMinTeD produced leaflets and material for legal aspects that accompany its services and composed the legal compatibility matrix of content, software, services to assist stakeholders. More information provided in the services section.

Figure 3: OpenMinTeD legal leaflets

2.6 Use cases

After the design and implementation of the technical parts of OpenMinTeD, the implementation and integration of the TDM applications that were designed around real-world problems were put forward by community partners. The project’s community work initially focused on four key thematic areas:

Table 1: OpenMinTeD Use Cases

Scholarly Communications	Life Sciences	Agriculture / Biodiversity	Social Sciences
SC-A: Research Analytics – Funding Mining Services, DataCite Linking, and Document Classification	LS-A: Extract Metabolites and their Properties and Modes of Actions	AS-A: Text mining over viticulture bibliographic data from AGRIS & CORE	SS-A: Facilitation of Complex Information Linking and Retrieval from Social Sciences Publications
SC-B: Research Publications Recommendation System	LS-B: Text Mining for Curation of Neuroscience Literature	AS-B: Text - mining over Food Safety & Water Health Bibliographic Data	
SC-C: Research Excellent Trends Explorer	LS-C: Text Mining on Articles Related to Health	AS-C: Microbial Biodiversity	

⁶ <http://www.meta-share.org/>

⁷ <https://www.clarin.eu/>

⁸ <https://www.elixir-europe.org/>

⁹ <http://einfracentral.eu/>

¹⁰ <https://www.fosteropenscience.eu/>

¹¹ <https://www.geant.org/>

¹² <https://www.eosc-hub.eu/>

	State Modelling in Chronic Liver Diseases		
SC-D: Rock Art Mining		AS-D: Linking Wheat Data With Literature	
SC-E: Text Mining of Articles Related to Leica Microscopes		AS-E: Extracting Gene Regulation Networks Involved in Seed Development (SeeDev)	

This process started with an assessment of the Communities requirements, which was used to influence the project's requirements and the design of the infrastructure. Next, an initial formalisation of the use cases was completed. These use cases were further formalised and specified, through collaboration of technical and community partners. A feasibility study was undertaken for each use case to see what is practical with current technologies. Based upon these use cases and feasibility studies we designed a set of applications.

Table 2. A detailed description of the integrated TDM applications

OpenMinTeD use cases applications

<p>SC-A: Research Analytics – Funding Mining Services, DataCite Linking, and Document Classification</p> <p>A multi-app consisted of the OpenAIRE inference services:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – The Funding Mining application mines the full text of publications and extracts links to projects. Currently, projects from FP7 and H2020 - EC, NSF and NIH - USA, Wellcome Trust and RCUK - UK, FCT - Portugal, ARC and NHMRC - Australia, CSF/HRZZ and MSES-MZOS - Croatia, SFI - Ireland, NOW - Netherlands are supported, updated with new funders on a regular basis. – The DataCite linking application mines the full text of publications and extracts links to DataCite. These links are mainly citations to datasets. – The Document Classification application mines the full text of publications in order to perform content-based classification using given taxonomies.
<p>SC-B: Research Publications Recommendation System</p> <p>Offers content-based recommendations to scholarly materials, such as related research papers. The recommender relies on metadata, full text features and other features that can be mined from the article full texts or are obtained from external sources, including citations, readership, affiliations, venues, publication year, etc. It is a standalone application that can be incorporated to a larger research information system.</p>
<p>SC-C: Research Excellent Trends Explorer</p> <p>Tracks research performance (citations counts) of papers, individuals, organisations, etc. delivered in the form of a dashboard. The application relies on access to the full texts and metadata to be able to</p>

OpenMinTeD use cases applications

slice and dice the data and extract full text features indicative of performance. The application creates the background data that can be used to create graphs allowing to perform benchmarking, comparison and trend analysis with regards to content and performance.

SC-D: Rock Art Mining

Assists researchers in finding ancient artistic artefacts in the archaeological scientific literature: rock paintings, petroglyphs, pictographs or engravings. The following properties are extracted: Artefact type, site name, date, dating method.

SC-E: Text Mining of Articles Related to Leica Microscopes

Using Leica microscopes this application identifies non article-based citations in the methodology section of an article.

LS-A: Extract Metabolites and their Properties and Modes of Actions

An application that recognises entities (species, metabolites, biological activity, spectral data, chemical, proteins) in an individual document. The workflow to detect the entities is named as “ChEBI curation web service - a machine learning-based workflow”, which is widely used for reference purposes in bioinformatics.

LS-B: Text Mining for Curation of Neuroscience Literature

Recognizes entities in neuroscience for a semi-automated curation process. Based on the public ontology <https://github.com/SciCrunch/NIF-Ontology>, it provides named entity recognition for the following entity types: Brain Region, Ionic Channel, Ionic Conductance, Ionic Current, Model Organism, Neuron, Scientific Unit, Scientific Value, five types of modelling parameters (Neuron Density, Maximal Ionic Conductance, Resting Membrane Potential, Volume of Brain Region, Ohmic Input Resistance).

LS-C: Text Mining on Articles Related to Health State Modelling in Chronic Liver Diseases

A proof of concept application that aids the definition of Chronic Diseases Health States: Non-Alcoholic Fatty Liver, Non-Alcoholic Steatohepatitis and End-state liver diseases. It extracts Chronic Liver Diseases articles from the data repository to identify article-based health states.

AS-A: Text mining over viticulture bibliographic data from AGRIS & CORE

Extraction of structured information (domain specific topics, images / figures, captions etc.) from unstructured bibliographic resources (i.e. PDF documents).

AS-B: Text-mining over Food Safety & Water Health Bibliographic Data

OpenMinTeD use cases applications

Extraction of geolocation information from unstructured bibliographic resources and RSS feeds targeting the Food Safety and Water Health Communities Two main ontological resources are used for assigning location URIs: Geonames (www.geonames.org) and the FAO Geopolitical Ontology (www.fao.org/countryprofiles/geoinfo/en/). The front-end application is a web-based viewer capable of projecting relevant information per selected country/region.

AS-C: Microbial Biodiversity

Complete the Florilege database which aims to gather, in a unified representation, public information on food products flora with a focus on positive flora (microorganisms involved in transformation, bioconservation or probiotics). The application extracts relevant spans of text and normalizes or categorizes with reference resources (*i.e.* taxonomy of organisms, ontology of habitat and ontology of phenotypes.) and entity linking.

AS-D: Linking Wheat Data with Literature

Feeds the database that supports semantic search engines with links between related in-house data and externally hosted texts. Identifies taxa, varieties, genes, markers and phenotypes. The phenotypes are automatically detected and normalized according to the two Wheat Phenotypes ontologies, WTO for text and WIPO for experimental data that have been aligned for querying.

AS-E: Extracting Gene Regulation Networks Involved in Seed Development (SeeDev)

The objective of the SeeDev TDM application is the extraction of information about plant seed development from scientific literature and combination with information of other sources in a unified way. It focuses on *Arabidopsis thaliana*, which is a small flowering plant used as a model organism by biologists. It first recognizes words that denote biological entities (gene, protein, RNA), then *normalize* them. Entities are then typed according to the knowledge model which formalizes the objects and their relations at stake in this specific use case. During the third step, the text-mining process allows to identify relations between the biological entities.

SS-A: Facilitation of complex information linking and retrieval from social sciences publications

Automatically detect named entities, recognize variable mentions and assign keywords from the thesaurus for the social sciences (TheSoz)¹³ to Semantically enrich and classify full texts in the GESIS publication repository.

TDM Components

¹³ TheSoz (<http://lod.gesis.org/thesoz/en.html>) offers a classification system with categories from the social sciences. The thesaurus contains about 12,000 entries with 8,000 descriptors and 4,000 synonyms.

Furthermore, in OpenMinTeD service and content provider systems aligned and registered in OpenMinTeD the following TDM components were registered;

Figure 4: OpenMinTeD TDM components frameworks

DKPro Core, a repository of UIMA components for NLP; a repository of GATE components for NLP, a subset of UIMA components for biomedical text mining that run remotely as web services, AlvisNLP framework components for text-mining and information extraction.

Many of these components have been deployed in the creation of new applications using the Galaxy workflow editor and the applications tested in OpenMinTeD with real data from the content offered in the platform.

2.7 Open Calls

Through two series of Open Calls, the first targeting content and the second software providers, more content and TDM tools were available in OpenMinTeD, registered and tested, resulting to a variety of assets and a creation of tutorials and courses. More specific:

Content providers

- Scielo; The Scielo proposal included the deployment of 14 national Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH) protocol endpoints (Argentina, Bolivia, Brazil, Chile, Colombia, Costa Rica, Cuba, Mexico, Paraguay, Peru, Portugal, Spain, Uruguay, Venezuela).
- IBECS: IBECS is a bibliographic dB with 150.000 registries, journals edited in Spain since 2000, health domain, abstracts.

Software providers

The following table illustrates the software providers that offered their applications:

Table 3: The Open Calls applications

Proposal Name	Domain	Language	Technology	Component integration
AgroPortal	Agriculture	EN	web service	NA
BabelNet_Extractor	General	multilingual	docker	UIMA wrapper
BTH-OGER	Life Sciences	EN	web service	NA
FIMDA	Life Sciences	EN	docker	UIMA wrapper
FreeLing_Integration	General	multilingual	docker	UIMA wrapper
IXA_pipes	General	multilingual	docker	XMI converter
PubMedRunner	Life Sciences	EN	docker	XMI converter

Proposal Name	Domain	Language	Technology	Component integration
Journalism	General	EN	maven	UIMA wrapper
RelationClassifier	Life Sciences	EN	docker	NA
Summarizer	General	EN	docker	Gate
TermSuite	Agriculture	EN	docker	XMI converter
UPFMT	General	EN	docker	XMI converter
VineSum	Agriculture	EN	maven	UIMA

2.8 The OpenMinTeD services

Through collaboration with the eInfraCentral project (www.einfracentral.eu) we developed our service catalogue and published it in the eInfraCentral catalogue service, which is to be the first instantiation of the EOSC catalogue.

2.8.1 OpenMinTeD catalogue of TDM applications¹⁴

A [catalogue of TDM applications](#) that users can browse through, refine the list contents with specific criteria using the faceted search or a google-like free text search facility, select a specific application and view its metadata description, with administrative and technical information (e.g. license, creator's name, contact information, specifications of the input and output resources, documentation and keywords). The catalogue targets users with little or no prior text mining

Figure 5: OpenMinTeD Catalogue of TDM Applications

experience that can search for, discover and easily re-use ready-to-run applications on content registered in the platform. Currently, the OpenMinTeD catalogue includes applications offered by the consortium partners and selected 13 third party providers (Annex III) - the winners of the OpenMinTeD Open Calls¹⁵. The differentiating feature from other software catalogues is that all applications can be executed with the OpenMinTeD applications execution service.

¹⁴ <https://services.openminted.eu/search;resourceType=application>

¹⁵ A full list and description of the open call winners is in the D2.5 – Open Call Programme Implementation Report (<http://openminted.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/06/D2.5-Open-Call-Programme-Implementation-Report-Final.pdf>)

2.8.2 OpenMinTeD catalogue of TDM components ¹⁶

Figure 6: OpenMinTeD Catalogue of TDM Components

The [catalogue of TDM components](#), i.e. pieces of software that perform basic tasks and can be reused to build applications, targets mainly TDM developers who know how to combine them together in order to build workflows with the OpenMinTeD workflow editor and finally offer them to end-users in the form of ready-to-use applications. As is the case with other OpenMinTeD catalogues, the service is empowered through browse and search (faceted and google-like free text) functionalities based on the metadata descriptions of the resources. Currently, this catalogue includes components offered by the consortium partners and the successful applicants of the OpenMinTeD Open Calls. All components have been adapted to follow the OpenMinTeD interoperability specifications. This a) ensures that they can be executed without problems in the platform, and b) facilitates their combination (when possible) with other components, in the same workflow, irrespective of their original implementation framework.

2.8.3 OpenMinTeD catalogue of TDM ancillary resources ¹⁷

Figure 7: OpenMinTeD Catalogue of TDM Ancillary resources

The catalogue of ancillary knowledge resources includes [Machine Learning \(ML\) models and computational grammars](#) ¹⁸ that can be combined with TDM software, as well as [annotation resources](#) ¹⁹, i.e. lexica, terminological lists, gazetteers, linguistic and domain ontologies, etc., that can be used for annotating content resources. Ancillary resources can be used together with generic TDM components to adapt to new domains or languages. Users can browse through the catalogue or use the faceted search or a keyword search text query to discover resources according to specific criteria.

¹⁶ <https://services.openminted.eu/search;resourceType=component>

¹⁷ <https://services.openminted.eu/search;resourceType=language;query=lexical>

¹⁸ <https://services.openminted.eu/search;resourceType=language>

¹⁹ <https://services.openminted.eu/resourceRegistration/lexical>

The catalogue brings together resources added by users or imported from domain community portals and registries, all appropriately described through a harmonised metadata schema. All the resources include links to the point(s) they can be accessed from and can be deployed to build TDM applications which can then be executed through the OpenMinTeD platform. Currently, the platform hosts resources offered by the consortium partners (mainly ML models), or publicly available registered by the winners of the Open Calls.

2.8.4 OpenMinTeD catalogue of corpora (datasets)²⁰

 The screenshot shows the OpenMinTeD web interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for HOME, SEARCH, ADD, PROCESS, SUPPORT, and SIGN IN | REGISTER. The main content area displays search results for 'Corpora (3)'. The results list three items: 'CHEBI CORPUS' (a sample corpus of 2 pdf files), 'TEST CORPUS WITH MULTIPLE FORMATS' (a sample corpus with pdf, txt and xml texts), and 'CC-BY TESTING CORPUS FOR THE NEUROSCIENCE USE CASE' (4 relevant CC-BY research articles). On the left, there are filters for RESOURCE TYPE (Corpora (3) is selected) and REFINE options for Licence (Creative Commons Attribution Non Commercial 4.0 (2), Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 (1)) and Rights Statement (Open Access (3)). A HELP sidebar on the right provides search tips.

A [catalogue of corpora](#), mainly datasets of open access scholarly publications, that are registered in the OpenMinTeD platform. Users can view publicly available corpora that are either created via the OpenMinTeD corpus builder service for scholarly works (see relevant subsection), or directly uploaded to the OpenMinTeD platform by users. The catalogue can be browsed and searched via the faceted navigation facility or a keyword search query. All users can view the descriptions of the

Figure 8: Catalogue of Scholarly datasets

corpora (with administrative and technical information, such as language, domain, keywords, license, resource creator, etc.), as well as the contents and, when available, the metadata descriptions of the individual files that compose them. In addition, registered users can process them with the TDM applications offered by OpenMinTeD and download them in accordance with their licensing conditions. The processability of the corpora is the asset of this catalogue in comparison with other catalogues that simply list corpora.

²⁰ <https://services.openminded.eu/search;resourceType=corpus>

2.8.5 OpenMinTeD corpus builder of scholarly works²¹

Figure 9: The OpenMinTeD corpus builder service

OpenMinTeD has set up a mechanism which provides access to scholarly and scientific content from a wide range of sources and enables users to search and select among them the ones that interest them for mining; the selection is based on a faceted search or a google-like natural text query while the selected documents form together a collection or "corpus". The OpenMinTeD registry provides content made available by two major content aggregators, [OpenAIRE](https://www.openaire.eu/)²² and [CORE](https://core.ac.uk/)²³, and will soon be complemented with content from successful applicants of the Open Calls. Currently there are around 14 million publications (full texts and abstracts) available²⁴.

2.8.6 OpenMinTeD TDM applications execution service²⁵

Figure 10: OpenMinTeD TDM Applications Executor

This service targets primarily researchers with little or no knowledge of text mining who need to find and run TDM applications on content without going through complicated processes. OpenMinTeD offers ready-to-use TDM applications in a catalogue that can be easily searched and browsed. Once users find the appropriate application, they can select to run it on their own content or on content offered in the OpenMinTeD platform.

²¹ <https://services.openminted.eu/resourceRegistration/corpus/searchForPublications>

²² <https://www.openaire.eu/>

²³ <https://core.ac.uk/>

²⁴ 13241538 publications on 14 May 2018

²⁵ <https://services.openminted.eu/runApplication>

2.8.7 OpenMinTeD builder of TDM applications²⁶

With the OMTD workflow editor, which is based on the [Galaxy editor²⁷](#), registered users can build new TDM applications by combining together various components. The service is intended for expert TDM developers who know which components can be put together and in which order based on their input and output requirements. OpenMinTeD has defined a set of specifications that aim to resolve interoperability issues stemming from the different implementation frameworks of the components. The specifications allow the integration of components in the form of dockerized images²⁸ as well as web services that abide to the OpenMinTeD specifications.

Figure 11: OpenMinTeD Builder of TDM Applications

2.8.8 OpenMinTeD TDM Support & Training²⁹

Figure 12: OpenMinTeD training and tutorials in FOSTER

The OpenMinTeD Support & Training services aim to (a) raise awareness about TDM among researchers and instruct them on how to integrate it in their research activities and workflows, and (b) promote the OpenMinTeD platform. We see a gap in this domain (i.e., training on TDM in general) and are considering this to be a potentially valuable service (accompanying the concrete OMTD

²⁶ <https://services.openminted.eu/resourceRegistration/application>

²⁷ <https://galaxyproject.org/>

²⁸ OpenMinTeD provides mechanisms for dockerising UIMA and GATE components.

²⁹ <http://openminted.eu/support-training/>

technical services). The OpenMinTeD services on TDM support & training include:

- [Frequently Asked Questions](#) about TDM and OpenMinTeD
- [Webinars](#) and presentation [material](#) on OpenMinTeD
- Tutorials & courses on OpenMinTeD
- [TDM stories](#) by researchers working in the TDM domain presenting the benefits of TDM and discussing various issues related to TDM
- [OpenMinTeD Knowledge Base](#) in the FOSTER platform
- appropriate links to the [Future TDM](#) project (e.g. Legal guidelines for TDM practitioners)
- [OpenMinTeD glossary](#) of TDM-related terms
- [OpenMinTeD resources site](#) with documentation related to the interoperability specifications, the OMTD-SHARE metadata schema, instructions for specific implementation frameworks, a list of the consortium partners' components, etc.
- The [OpenMinTeD Guidelines](#) promote the OpenMinTeD interoperability specifications among content and software providers. They provide instructions on how they can make their assets compliant with the specifications and how to share them through the OpenMinTeD platform.

2.8.9 OpenMinTeD license compatibility matrix³⁰

Figure 13: OpenMinTeD Licenses compatibility matrix

Catering for legal interoperability, OpenMinTeD has elaborated a license compatibility matrix³¹, a service that expands its usage beyond OpenMinTeD. This matrix has been developed by the legal partners of OpenMinTeD and validated by external legal experts involved in the respective working group ([WG3 - IPR and Licensing Issues](#)³²). It demonstrates the compatibility among available licenses on content, software and services. As explained, “The matrix aims at assessing the possibility that the content licensed under the licences hereby considered may be combined and their combination feasibly result in a derivative work. The matrix also assesses whether, considering some specific clauses (e.g. NC or SA), there is likely to be a conflict between the licensing terms considered.”

³⁰ <https://openminted.github.io/releases/license-matrix/>

³¹ The final version of the compatibility matrix is completed at the end of May 2018

³² <http://openminted.eu/community/working-groups/>

3. Technical developments

3.1 Platform Design & Portal

Platform Design and Implementation and user interface

The major layers and components of the platform were identified in the overall platform architecture. During the first period of the project the main functionalities of the registry were specified based on the user requirements from the four participating domain specific communities, which led to the design and implementation of the core services. The user interface (UI) and the user experience (UX) of the platform (<https://services.openminded.eu/home>) was designed by considering the functional specifications, as well as the results of the OMTD-Share internal data model.

Distribution, optimization and parallelization

The OpenMinTeD platform and infrastructure, including text mining tools, services and associated resources was deployed on the cloud infrastructure using state of the art technologies (e.g., docker, Mesos), which allowed for optimized service deployment and execution via scalable VM-based service distribution and storage performed.

Parallelization of TDM runs (i.e., a particular service operation) requires further work as the TDM services themselves have to be adapted accordingly and support parallel execution environments (e.g. Spark).

3.2 Interoperability & Guidelines

Interoperability

The OpenMinTeD interoperability framework defined and presented in a user-friendly specification to empower interoperability between content and software resources, was achieved through the OpenMinTeD guidelines (guidelines.openminded.eu). This effectively defines two aspects:

- The OMTD-SHARE data model which provides metadata description for a. scientific literature (compatible with OpenAIRE guidelines v3.0), b. software services (to be seen: compatibility with pending OpenAIRE guidelines for software, Software Heritage and Software Sustainability guides and best practices), and c. ancillary resources.
- Best practices and guides on how to register software components on the platform: docker, maven, web services

3.3 AAI

Authorization authentication infrastructure was implemented based on the emerging EOSC standards. Based on the EGI check-in service and following the AARC standard, the OMTD AAI allows users to login via their academic account EduGain, their ORCID or other social media accounts. A set of roles has been integrated into the system (e.g., TDM expert, content provider, moderator) to allow for different types of usage of resources.

Moreover, an account and monitoring service, which can monitor the hardware resources that are used by the users, either when storing corpora and TDM resources or when executing applications implemented.

3.4 Registry and content registry

The Registry service is the core service responsible for bridging the text mining tools, workflows, and applications along with all their accompanying resources. A flexible and extensible component, it is able to accept different or new types of objects, allows for automated and real time validation of ingested objects according to the OMTD-Share schema, and supports subscriptions and notifications for an interactive user engagement.

On top of the registry we have built additional services that allow users to build corpora via APIs:

- The **content service** is responsible for building corpora with publications coming from external sources, allowing users to upload and process their own Open Access corpora,
- The **TDM connector** is responsible for retrieving metadata of TDM resources and tools from external sources that abide to the OMTD-SHARE schema, and
- The **content connector** is responsible for the interaction with the external content sources, that directly access OpenAIRE and CORE metadata and fetch full text/content from them.

3.5 Workflow service

After consideration of different workflow engines, the Galaxy TDM **Workflow service** was selected to be integrated in the platform, primarily due to its editor. The Galaxy service was adjusted to work with the registry for seamless interaction with the registry and AAI, and the underlying cloud infrastructure. It effectively allows expert users to build new TDM applications by re-using TDM components available in OpenMinTeD.

3.6 Annotations

Annotation and crowdsourcing services

An annotation tool viewer is integrated in OpenMinTeD to allow users view annotations over corpora.

The annotations tool used on top of the platform is WebAnno a general-purpose web-based annotation tool. Furthermore, the specification of the AERO protocol, an API that specifies how an annotation editor can be integrated with the OpenMinTeD platform (or any other platform that needs to include an annotation editor) was achieved. WebAnno (and also AlvisAE, an annotation editor developed by INRA) was enhanced with AERO support and in the Registry a client was created for an AERO supporting annotation editor. The result was that the platform can be easily deployed along with WebAnno or AlvisAE and provide support for annotation editing.

3.7 Platform Integration

OpenMinTeD combines and integrates various software engineering processes and artifacts that are required for integrating the OpenMinTeD services into a single functional entity. The main parts of the system are its Catalogue, Storage, Cloud, Executor, Workflow Editor. Technical information is provided in a dedicated GitHub³³.

3.8 Cloud infrastructure

OpenMinTeD is built on GRNET ~okeanos IaaS cloud infrastructure, using the Apache MESOS software that allocates and assigns necessary resources (VMs and storage) on demand and deploys and operates the supporting services: AAI, monitoring and accounting. This will be furthermore updated following GRNET's cloud update with open stack.

³³ <https://github.com/openminded>

4. Preparing for the future

4.1 Sustainability and business model study

A techno-economic model³⁴ based on well-established methodology, assumptions, cost and revenues, OpenMinTeD services and policies, provided results of the economic sustainability of the OpenMinTeD platform for two selected use cases. In the first use case the OpenMinTeD platform is a distributed service that serves local research communities on demand (Software-as-a-Service or SaaS), a part of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)³⁵, including a Text and Data

Mining (TDM) catalogue allowing users to search and find TDM applications, services and content. In the second use case, OpenMinTeD introduces commercial TDM services which will be able to run using other data sets apart from the Open Access research publication content of the first use case.

The approach preferred for the future is a hybrid one for OpenMinTeD, where both EU funds, support from consortium and industry can place OpenMinTeD centrally in the EU-Infrastructures map. OpenMinTeD needs to continue running its core services based on Cloud infrastructure and having support from its current and future partners.

4.2 OpenMinTeD within EOSC

OpenMinTeD is an e-Infrastructure. E-infrastructures are long-term strategic investments within the RIs in Europe, at all levels, deeply rooted in society, and indispensable both for enabling and developing excellence in their respective scientific domains - TDM in this case. E-Infrastructures and RIs are also key players contributing to competitiveness of Europe with a very large perimeter of applications. OpenMinTeD may have a tremendous impact on skills and education agendas increasing the competences of researchers, industry and can improve the perception and understanding of science and technology in society at large by demonstrating various use cases of TDM. Some specialized TDM applications may be on:

- Research fields that assist the well-nighness and well-being of society and solve major societal needs (health, food safety, transportations, security, communication, insurance, immigration, diplomacy, and more).

³⁴ D2.4 - Draft Sustainability model study

³⁵ EOSC will be a trusted environment with federated services supporting research data activities in all stages of the research lifecycle

- Industries that strive to find what is important out of massive scientific content and map that with their needs (pharmaceutical, media, food)

EU Infrastructures

OpenMinTeD has a central position in the Open Science ecosystem, as it has all the potential to be a “TDM Hub” for scientific literature within the EOSC ecosystem.

Figure 14 specifically illustrates how OpenMinTeD is placed among existing EU infrastructures, providing a gluing mechanism for researchers, SMEs and industry, to access content in a secure way and mine it on the cloud.

Figure 14: OpenMinTeD position among EU Infrastructures and within EOSC Ecosystem

4.3 Contact us

For further information and any inquiries, social media and supporting tools of OpenMinTeD operate.

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